

NON-DESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES - AN OVERVIEW

by

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ABSTRACT

Composites have now been employed as structural materials for many years and it might be imagine that it is readily possible to define what constitutes a defect, and perhaps also to suggest how this defect might be detected, and maybe even characterised non-destructively. One of the major advantages of composite materials, however, lies in the fact that the material can be tailored to meet a particular application. Thus, even using carefully specified fibre and matrix materials, there can still be components exhibiting widely different lay-ups, thicknesses and volume fractions. The result of this is that a feature which constitutes a serious defect in one component could be entirely acceptable in another. When to this you add the fact that new or improved fibres and resins are continually being introduced it becomes clear that setting quality control and inspection standards is not a simple matter.

This paper will not therefore attempt to provide a comprehensive review of the problems and potential of non-destructive evaluation of composites; this has already been done very effectively elsewhere (see for example References 1 & 2). Instead it will consider one important class of composites - continuous fibres in organic matrices - and will examine the ways in which these can fail and the effects of defects on structural performance. On the basis of this, requirements for inspection will be proposed and methods of meeting these requirements reviewed. Because of the authors' background strong emphasis will be placed on aerospace applications, but it is considered that this is justified because these applications are among the most demanding for materials of this class. Furthermore, most of the principles involved are equally valid for other applications, even though practical considerations may mean that the NDT techniques selected do differ. Initial consideration will be given to the capability of some of the leading methods before examining how these methods can be simplified for production or in-service inspection.

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DEFECTS

When considering the role of defects in the failure process it is necessary to distinguish between those defects that act on a microscopic level and those which are of real importance in a multi-angle fabrication or a practical component. The role of the former may well appear quite significant if judged on the basis of quality control tests on test pieces fabricated with a simple uni-directional lay-up, and yet have little relevance to the requirements for practical NDT. Consider, for example, the role played by porosity in the matrix. Several years ago it was noted that even a low level of porosity could have a dramatic effect on the interlaminar shear strength of CFC (Carbon Fibre Composites), as measured by a short beam shear test on uni-directional material³. As a result of this, considerable effort was expended on developing accurate non-destructive methods of detecting and quantifying porosity. More recently, however, it was realised that in real components with complex multi-directional lay-ups the role of porosity was far less significant^{4&5}. Furthermore, as will be shown shortly, the acceptable strain levels in these components tend to be governed by design features such as fastener holes or by the possibility of impact damage occurring. Even quite high levels (5%) of porosity then have little influence.

However, a degree of caution is necessary because the level of porosity may be important if local compressive failure is a possibility. Furthermore, there is now a trend towards the use of tougher resins which are less impact sensitive, and towards fabrications which are entirely adhesively bonded thus avoiding the stress concentrations induced by fastener holes. Both of these trends encourage the use of higher strain levels and defects which are currently considered tolerable may not necessarily be so in the future.

The requirements for inspection can only be established by having an adequate understanding of the possible failure modes that could occur and of the role that defects play in these mechanisms.

FAILURE MECHANISMS AND THE ROLE OF DEFECTS IN MULTI-ANGLE LAMINATES

It is often convenient to consider a composite as an assembly of identifiably separate plies, each having its fibres aligned in a specific direction. For carbon fibre composites fabricated from pre-preg such a model is reasonable, but procedures such as filament winding or wet lay-up of woven cloth will clearly result in a composite which departs somewhat from the simple model. However, the use of this model does permit a better understanding of the principal failure mechanisms and hence of the role of defects. Each mechanism will be briefly examined in turn.

Axial Tensile Failure

This is dominated by the tensile strength of the fibres and by the degree of their alignment with the loading axis. The matrix properties do not in general have much effect and, although the strength of the fibre to matrix bond may cause quite a change in appearance of the fracture surface, it does not really change the tensile strength.

Defects do not have a very significant effect on the tensile strength, although twisted or kinked fibre tows will reduce the strength somewhat. The effect of service damage is really dependent simply on the number of 0° fibres - that is to say the load carrying fibres - that are cut at a given section.

Axial Compressive Strength

The axial compressive strength of a multi-directional laminate does not really do what might be expected. The compressive strength of uni-directional XAS-914 CFC material is about 1500 MNm. It might therefore be expected that in a multi-directional laminate all of the 0° plies would be capable of carrying this stress, so that as we add more and more $\pm 45^\circ$ plies the compressive strength of the laminate would decrease in a way following a simple rule of mixtures - and this was indeed what used to happen with the last generation of materials. However, as Figure 1 shows, this does not happen with the modern material until you get down to about 70% of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. The exact explanation for this is uncertain but it appears that interlaminar shear failure may occur, allowing macrobuckling of the 0° plies before they have reached their compressive strength.

Figure 1 Variation of Compressive Strength with Percentage of $\pm 45^\circ$ PLYS

The point to note is that the compressive strength of the whole laminate is governed by the stability of the 0° plies and this will be strongly affected by the presence of damage, and in particular by delaminations.

In-plane Shear Failure and Transverse Failure

In a simple uni-directional laminate both the in-plane shear strength and the transverse strength depend on the continuity of the

matrix and of the fibre-matrix interface so they are most severely affected by defects such as translaminar cracks - that is to say splitting parallel to the fibres.

However, in a multi-directional laminate the in-plane shear and transverse loads are usually carried by tensile and compressive stresses parallel to the fibres in suitably aligned plies so that the sensitivity to defects is much the same as the two cases that we have already discussed.

Interlaminar Shear Failure and Peel Failure

Both of these mechanisms are concerned with separation at a plane interface, either that between plies in a laminate or at a bond-line in a fabricated component. It is clear therefore that anything which weakens this interface must be regarded as a potential defect. There are in fact two major types. First there is the simple delamination or separation between plies; this is, of course, an area of zero strength and a stress concentration. The other type is a bond having weak adhesive or cohesive strength. The assessment of bond strength is, however, a difficult task which will be discussed later in this paper.

Failure at Structural Features

The above summary refers to areas of straightforward multi-angle laminates subjected to relatively uniform in-plane stress. For such areas it can be seen that by far the most important defect is the presence of delamination. In a real structure of course there is a wide range of what might be termed structural features at which the stress patterns are more complex. In particular, stresses can be generated normal to the plane of the laminate. The role of defects at such structural features can be quite complex and there are significant MOD funded programmes under way at present which are attempting to clarify and quantify this. At present it can only be said that such areas may be less tolerant to defects.

AN INTRODUCTION TO INSPECTION

Inspection Requirements

The complexity of composite components can vary very widely from a simple GRP storage tank to a sophisticated aerospace component involving a variety of materials and a very complex lay-up. The specific design of each component must therefore be considered in order to identify which of the above failure criteria is relevant and to understand the role which defects could play. No general statement can be made. Having said that, however, it must be recognised that our current understanding of the role of defects is far from complete, and in many cases the requirements for inspection are based on a knowledge that past components containing certain defects have performed satisfactorily. To illustrate the approach that is currently being adopted consideration will be given to the requirements for two types of critical aerospace component.

Take first a CFC wing box for a fighter aircraft. The box is primarily designed to take bending and torsional loads and the skin will typically be fabricated from pre-preg having lay-up directions of 0° (spanwise), 90° , and $\pm 45^\circ$. The lay-up is carefully tailored and the skin will taper from a thickness of say 15 mm at the root to 5 mm at the tip. The skin is also pierced by various fastener holes so notch effects are important. There are three basic design criteria for such a component.

- (1) Low temperature static notch tensile strength.
- (2) Elevated temperature notch compressive static or fatigue strength.
- (3) Local or overall buckling.

These criteria are currently met by specifying a design strain level of about ± 4000 microstrain. This is intended to accommodate features such as the fastener holes but does in fact enable quite large defects to be tolerated. The authors have considered this in more detail elsewhere⁵ and concluded that, at least in areas of fairly uniform stress, the only defect likely to be of structural significance is an area of delamination > 20 mm diameter. The detection of such a defect would present no problem to production inspection.

In service the usual cause of delaminations is impact damage which can only occur on accessible surfaces. Furthermore, it is very difficult to induce damage of this nature without leaving a surface indentation. It is, however, not impossible if a large radius indenter is employed. The authors were able to produce an area of damage 60 mm x 50 mm in the 4 mm CFC skin of a wing box by dropping a 75 mm diameter steel ball from a height of 1.6 metres. There was no surface indication whatsoever. This does, however, correspond to an impact energy of 28 J, or 7 J/mm of thickness, which is much higher than the levels usually regarded as tolerable. It highlights the importance of performing the test on a structure that can dissipate much of the incident energy, rather than on a simple panel.

It appears therefore that although the detection of damage in a wing skin can largely be done by visual inspection it will be necessary to make a careful assessment of the nature of the threat before eliminating the requirement to detect hidden or barely visible impact damage. Whichever way the damage is detected it will be necessary to use NDT to size or otherwise characterise the damage. It will be shown later that this can be achieved at various levels of sophistication, varying from an approximate measurement of the area of the skin that exhibits some degree of delamination, to a full assessment of the through-thickness distribution of delaminations and identification of the associated translaminar cracks.

Consider now the problem of inspecting a composite rotor blade for a helicopter. This has to withstand various combinations of centrifugal loading, bending (flap and lag), and torsion, and a wide variety of designs has been produced. Figure 2 shows an example of a modern UK design demonstrating how the complex loading demands a

complicated combination of carbon and glass fibre at various orientations, some material being woven. Features such as metallic erosion shields and heater mats introduce further complications and limit the NDT techniques that can be employed. It is possible for various defects to be induced; these are mostly in the form of shrinkage cracks or areas of quite gross porosity, although fibre waviness can also be a problem. However, the majority of the blade is designed to meet a stiffness criterion and is usually overstrength. The result of this is that quite large defects can be tolerated.

Figure 2 Section of Helicopter Rotor Blade

Figure 3 X-Radiograph of Blade Section

NDT is used extensively during development of the blade manufacturing process when detailed cross-sectional views of the spar structure are very valuable (Fig 3). Production inspection, however, is aimed not at a detailed identification of individual defects, but at a broader characterisation of material quality. X-radiography and fluoroscopy are widely used to ensure that the quality is at least as good as that of components which have proved to be acceptable in mechanical tests.

In order to do this a "library" of radiographs of components containing various defects has been built up, against which individual radiographs may be compared. These quality control checks are usually underpinned by selecting, say, 1 in 40 blades from a production run for destructive evaluation and strength testing.

To an even greater extent than with the wing skin, in-service inspection of composite rotor blades relies on visual inspection. Ideally, if there is no clear indication of damage, then the blade is acceptable; visible damage must be repaired. This simple ideal may eventually prove to have limitations and it should be noted that various forms of in-service NDT are feasible if required.

The Applicability of Inspection Methods

A large number of inspection methods have been applied to composite materials but in practice two methods have been used much more widely than any of the others - namely, ultrasonic inspection and X-radiography. However, despite their widespread use, it is the authors' experience that many specialists in composites are not sufficiently familiar with these techniques to appreciate fully their capabilities and limitations. For both these reasons ultrasonics and radiography will be examined in some detail before proceeding to a briefer review of some alternative methods.

ULTRASONICS

Conventional Ultrasonic Techniques

Energy Transfer

A common feature of all techniques is the requirement to couple the transducer to the specimen in such a way that the transfer of energy into and out of the specimen is maximised. The efficiency of this coupling depends on the acoustic properties of the various materials involved. If you take for example a water/CFC (or CFC/water) interface then some 73% of the incident energy is transmitted. It is often convenient, therefore, to immerse both the specimen and the transducer in a water bath. Failing this, however, a grease or gel couplant is usually satisfactory. Consider now a CFC/air interface. This time only 0.03% of the energy is transmitted and 99.97% is reflected. Because of this, air-filled delaminations give rise to strong echoes and an air-backed laminate can readily be inspected from one side.

Immersion Testing

In some cases the use of a gel-coupled contact transducer is unavoidable but immersion systems do have a number of advantages. Not only is the coupling constant, but the fact that the transducer may be located some distance away from the surface of the specimen permits the use of transducers producing focused or collimated beams. The transducer is held in a manipulator so that its orientation and distance from the specimen can be adjusted. The transducer can then be used to scan in a prescribed plane relative to the specimen surface. Information can be obtained about the condition of the specimen and presented in a number of ways, the most usual being the so-called A, B and C-scan displays. These presentations are also applicable to non-immersion systems, but are more difficult to achieve in practice.

Ultrasonic A-scan

The A-scan technique, displayed on an oscilloscope screen, is perhaps the simplest method of presenting ultrasonic information. The horizontal base line indicates elapsed time while the heights of vertical deflections represent intensity of echoes. The heart of the

equipment used to generate this information is an ultrasonic test-set. This instrument contains the necessary electronics to excite the transmitter, to receive and amplify the signals generated by a receiver, and to display the resulting information on an oscilloscope screen.

In general, ultrasonic energy is both transmitted through the specimen and reflected from it. The transmitted energy may be detected by a separate transducer located on the far side of the specimen, in which case the procedure is called 'through-transmission'; alternatively the reflected energy may be detected by the same transducer acting as both transmitter and receiver, and in this case the procedure is called 'pulse-echo'. In either case the received acoustic energy is converted into electrical energy by the receiving transducer and is amplified and displayed by the test-set. Most production inspection of composite components is performed in the through-transmission mode allowing a greater thickness of material to be inspected. For in-service inspection access is often limited to one side of a component, in which case a pulse-echo technique must be used.

If the amplitudes of the ultrasonic waves received by the transducer are converted into electrical signals, rectified and displayed as the vertical deflection on an oscilloscope screen while the horizontal deflection corresponds to time, then an A-scan display is produced. This will consist of a series of spikes whose position along the horizontal axis can be calibrated in terms of depth in the sample under test so that the position of a reflector can be measured. The amplitude of each echo will give some indication of the size and nature of the reflector.

The A-scan shown in Figure 4 is the type of display that is produced when the ultrasonic pulses are of short duration so that individual reflections do not merge together. In this figure the first pulse (a) is largest and is due to the electrical pulse used to excite the transducer and is a convenient reference for timing subsequent reflections. The next pulse (b) is due to energy being reflected from the front face of the sample. The separation between these pulses corresponds to the time taken for the sound to travel in the water from the transducer to the specimen and back. Echo (d) is due to energy being reflected from the back face of the sample and is separated from (b) by a delay which corresponds to the propagation time through the sample. Any defect echoes present will appear between (b) and (d) as at (c) in the figure. The relative amplitudes of the echoes can, with care, be used to assess the attenuation of sound due to propagation through the sample.

The resolution with which the through-thickness position of a reflector can be estimated is dependent on the wavelength and the duration of the ultrasonic pulse emitted by the transducer. The lateral dimensions of the volume of material examined depend on the divergence of the ultrasonic beam generated by the transducer, its size in relation to the ultrasonic wavelength and the distance between the sample and the transducer.

To ensure that energy reflected from the specimen returns to the transducer when used in the pulse-echo mode, the transducer is adjusted so that the sound beam is aligned normal to the plane of the specimen by changing its orientation until the return echoes are maximized. This process is called normalization.

The A-scan type of display can also be used without an immersion tank when the ultrasonic transducer is coupled to the specimen by a thin grease or gel film. The transducer can then be moved and the change in the display noted. This is the normal method used for the inspection of composites when the transducer is manipulated manually. It is, however, more difficult to use the technique to obtain accurate measurements; this is partly due to variations in the coupling film.

It is important to note that, if a defect is present and is of a type that reflects a large fraction of the incident soundwave, then only a very small proportion will propagate beyond the defect. Any additional reflections will be small and will usually not be detected. The result is that the material in the shadow region behind the first defect will not be inspected and additional defects will not be found. This effect is especially noticeable with impact damage which causes multiple delaminations.

Ultrasonic B-scan

If the same transducer is moved linearly, (usually by a motor drive) in a plane parallel to that of the specimen then a number of A-scans can be recorded corresponding to different positions across the specimen. It is however more convenient to extract the essential features of the A-scans, namely, the position and amplitude of the major peaks, and to combine them in a single display. This type of display is called a B-scan and the basic principle may be understood by reference to Figure 5. The display is usually presented on a storage oscilloscope, as shown, so that the horizontal deflection is proportional to the transducer position, the vertical deflection is proportional to time (or depth through the sample) and the stored intensity is modulated by the amplitude of the received reflections. It can be seen that the display corresponds to a slice taken through the sample, normal to the surface.

Figure 4 A-Scan Presentation

Figure 5 B-Scan Presentation

With the B-scan type of presentation it is possible to estimate both the depth of reflectors and their lateral extent along the axis of transducer movement. The depth resolution is dependent on the same factors as for the A-scan technique, while the lateral resolution depends upon the transducer beam profile and the step size used for lateral movement. It should be noted that, as with the A-scan technique, the shadow region behind a large defect will not be inspected and this must be remembered when interpreting B-scans.

Ultrasonic C-scan

The third type of ultrasonic technique that might be employed is the C-scan. In this type of presentation a more complex scanning system is used such that the transducer is scanned in a plane parallel to the specimen in a rectilinear raster pattern (Fig 6). The recorder pen is coupled to the transducer manipulator so that the pen accurately reproduces the scanning pattern.

In an immersion system the transducer is scanned in the water tank above the specimen. If a single transducer is employed in the pulse-echo configuration a glass reflector plate placed behind the specimen is often used. In this case the echo amplitude plotted corresponds to that of the ultrasonic pulse that has propagated through the specimen, been reflected by the glass reflector plate, again propagated through the specimen and returned to the transducer. Hence the amplitude of this signal corresponds to that of a wave that has travelled through the specimen twice and for this reason the technique is called a double through-transmission technique (Fig 7). Because this mis-match in acoustic impedance between the water and glass is so large very little energy is transmitted into the glass and so in most instances it can be considered as a perfect reflector.

Figure 6 C-Scan Presentation

Figure 7 The Double Through-Transmission Technique

This system has the advantage that to a good approximation, neglecting for instance changes in the surface reflectivity of the specimen, the amplitude of the glass reflection can be considered as proportional to the attenuation of sound in the specimen. The received signal echo from the glass plate is also well separated in time from other reflections and hence is easy to monitor. This is done by using a time gate which converts the amplitude of the largest reflection within a preset time interval to a voltage, which is fed to the recorder. The clear separation of the glass signal permits the use of a time gate whose width is large enough to accommodate variations in the specimen thickness or in the distances between the transducer, specimen and glass.

Other gating techniques can be used. For example, the attenuation due to the specimen can be monitored by gating the back wall reflection. However this echo is located close to other echoes, and a more precise gate is required.

The C-scan map is often plotted on current-sensitive recording paper producing a grey-scale presentation with the density plotted depending upon the amplitude of the gated signal. Because this type of recording paper will only reproduce a limited grey-scale range the plotted density range is usually divided into a small number of distinct grey levels. This is achieved by the use of an electronic quantiser consisting of a parallel bank of voltage comparators with adjustable thresholds. As the signal amplitude increases the comparators trigger in succession causing a step change in the recording current and hence the plotted density. The relative separation of these thresholds can be varied as desired. Not only does this technique accommodate the limited grey range of the recording paper but it also produces recordings that are more easily interpreted than continuous grey-scale recordings and so the technique is often used even with other types of recording media. Alternatively the attenuation data may be stored in a computer and various colour presentations are now available. Simple displays require the arbitrary selection of a limited range of colours and are not always easy to interpret, but more sophisticated systems can offer a significant increase in the dynamic range displayed. The big advantage of computer storage, however, is the ability to produce, from a single scan, presentations corresponding to different attenuation thresholds. Whether or not computer storage is used it is important to note that the threshold settings are arbitrary and by comparatively small changes quite different C-scans can be produced. The C-scan will only be meaningful if the relationship between the settings and the parameter plotted is known by calibration.

If the glass reflector signal is selected, the resulting C-scan map is related to the attenuation of ultrasound in the specimen and might appear as in Figure 8a with the defects shown as light areas. Alternatively if a narrow width gate is used and positioned between the front and backwall echoes it is possible to produce a recording showing the presence of internal reflections from flaws as dark areas (Fig 8b).

It can be appreciated that the C-scan presentation gives a good estimate of the lateral extent of a defect in plan view, the resolution depending upon the same parameters as for the B-scan. No information is presented on the depth position of any defects. This information can only be inferred from the position and selectivity (width) of the time gate employed.

Figure 8a C-Scan of Glass Reflected Signal

Figure 8b C-Scan of Defects Only

Figure 8c B-Scan Along Line 'e'

Figure 8(c) shows a B-scan presentation of the cross-section along line "e", and the through-thickness distribution of damage can be clearly seen.

Problems of Immersion Techniques

There are disadvantages in using immersion testing equipment some of which are listed below.

- (1) Immersion tanks become very large and expensive for large components like an aircraft wing skin.
- (2) Honeycomb structure, because of the entrapped air, floats and keeping large structures immersed is difficult.
- (3) The alignment of the transducer relative to the specimen is critical, which makes the inspection of shaped items difficult.
- (4) The component is contaminated with water.

Alternative techniques are therefore applied to overcome some of these problems when they are critical for a particular application.

Ultrasonic Jet-Probes

A commonly used technique, which still uses water as a couplant, is the jet-probe technique illustrated in Figure 9. Here the component is not immersed, instead the coupling water impinges onto the surface of the component in a jet along which the ultrasound travels. The water jet acts as a waveguide to the sound. The main difficulty is to make sure, by correct design of the probe assembly, that the water flow is laminar. Because the sound is guided down the water jet awkward structural geometries can be inspected by employing suitably shaped guide-tubes. This technique is generally used in through-transmission and at frequencies below about 10 MHz. Although a jet-probe system looks quite different from an immersion system, the basic considerations are the same with the exceptions already noted. Certainly it is the most popular technique used in the aerospace industry for producing through-transmission C-scan of large components.

Figure 9 Schematic of Ultrasonic Jet Probes

Roller-probes

In applications where the composite must not come into contact with water, roller-probes can be used. The ultrasonic transducer element is held inside a wheel and the sound propagated into the specimen through a soft rubber tyre. This technique is generally used at low frequencies and can be used for the rapid detection of in-service damage but is not really suitable for its detailed characterization.

Specialized Ultrasonic Techniques

The techniques that have been described are the ones that are regularly used for much of the inspection carried out at present. There are, however, a number of other techniques that have been or are being developed for composite inspection and these will be briefly reviewed and their areas of application outlined.

Multi-element Transducers

This is the form of transducer commonly used in medical applications where a large number of piezoelectric elements are incorporated in a single scanning head and are either pulsed sequentially or in discrete blocks. The output is normally displayed on a storage oscilloscope as a B-scan and has the obvious attraction of covering a large area rapidly and offering greater mechanical stability than the normal single element hand-held delay-line transducer. It has been necessary to raise the frequency of medical units for their use in NDT and there are now currently available units with 108 focusing elements operating at frequencies up to 10 MHz, although 5 MHz is most commonly used for general composite inspection.

Shadow System

This technique⁶ uses soft-tipped probes, no couplant, and normally employs a pair of roller-probes mechanically linked in some way operating at approximately 1.5 MHz. The basic principle is to transmit broadband ultrasound into the material and then to modify the received signal by passing it through a tuneable filter with a bandwidth of about 10 kHz. This provides an ability to tune the system to maximum resonance dependent on component design and then to monitor changes in amplitude and phase that would indicate a defect. Probes can be used in through-transmission or pulse-echo and the technique is particularly suited to the rapid scanning of composite-skinned honeycomb structures.

Stress Wave Factor

The stress wave factor (SWF) technique seeks to characterise a composite by investigating the way in which it modifies an ultrasonic pulse that travels through it. Pulses of ultrasound are injected into the component from a transducer and are detected some distance away on the same side of the component. The pulses are treated as simulated acoustic emissions and are detected and processed as such. The SWF is then computed from the product of the repetition rate of the pulses,

the number of times the received pulse exceeds a preset threshold voltage (ring down count) and the duration of a preset timing interval. It has been reported that the SWF can be correlated with various material properties including tensile and interlaminar shear strength⁷.

Acoustic Backscattering

In this technique the scattering of sound waves back along their incident path is measured as a function of the orientation of the transducer. Results show that the technique can be used to identify fibre orientations since a maximum is observed in the reflected amplitude when the ultrasound is incident normal to the fibre axis. Fibre waviness and cracks can also be detected⁸.

Polar Scans

The polar scan displays the attenuation of a received signal as a brightness modulation on a polar display when the angle of incidence is varied to cover the angles of a half sphere. The resulting picture is rather complicated and, at present, impossible to predict theoretically. However, it is reported⁹ to provide a unique fingerprint of a specific laminate, being sensitive to ply stacking order and fibre orientation.

Velocity Measurement

Measurements of wave velocity in composites have been made by a number of workers and it has the advantage of being simple to measure accurately in all but very thin specimens. It has been suggested that the velocity normal to the fibres is sensitive to fibre volume fraction and matrix porosity and also to the state of cure for some resin systems¹⁰. Some theoretical work has suggested that for CFC a combination of velocity measurements can be used to measure volume fraction and porosity separately. These techniques have not been applied widely possibly because the effects are rather small.

Laser Techniques

It has been demonstrated by a number of workers (see, for example, references 11 and 12) that ultrasound can be generated and detected in metals using lasers and it seems possible that the same techniques can be applied to composites. The main advantages of such systems are that transducers do not need to be in contact with the sample or coupled to it by a water path, the generation and reception of ultrasound is comparatively insensitive to the orientation of the sample relative to the laser beams, and scanning systems can be mechanically simple and fast. Otherwise the ultrasonic principles of the systems are much the same as those already mentioned although there is little control over the shape of the ultrasonic beam. The disadvantages are the cost, the size of laser required, and the associated danger of producing surface damage. These are the main reasons why, to date, these systems have not found wide application.

Imaging Systems

A considerable amount of work is being carried out into ultrasonic imaging systems and some is aimed at imaging damage in composites. As has been stated, delaminations are of prime importance when considering possible damage in CFC aerospace structures. Recent work at RAE¹³ has been aimed at developing an ultrasonic imaging system in order to gain a better understanding of the nature of delaminations in composite materials. Briefly this system uses a combination of the B and C-scan methods to generate isometrically projected images of defects as pseudo three-dimensional displays. The software package within this system enables the viewer to select viewing angle and rotational position of the object as well as an option to magnify. Both the area and through-thickness position of the damage can therefore be viewed with a clarity not possible by conventional ultrasonic techniques. Figure 10 gives an example of the system's potential on a drilled acrylic calibration specimen. The ability to present information on impact damage in a CFC specimen is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10 Image of Calibration Sample

Figure 11 Image of Impact Damage in CFC

RADIOGRAPHY

Conventional Radiography

This technique is based on differential absorption of penetrating radiation by the object being inspected. Because of variations in thickness of the part, or differences in absorption characteristics caused by variations in composition, different portions of a test piece absorb different amounts of penetrating radiation. Unabsorbed radiation passing through the part can be recorded on film, or photosensitive paper, viewed on a fluorescent screen, or monitored by various types of radiation detectors.

In conventional radiography, an object is bombarded by a beam of X-rays and the portion of the radiation that is not absorbed by the object impinges on a sheet of film. The unabsorbed radiation exposes the film emulsion in just the same way that light exposes film in photography. Development of the film produces an image that is a two-dimensional "shadow picture" of the object. When inspection involves viewing of a real time image on a fluorescent screen or image intensifier, the radiographic process is termed fluoroscopy.

Generally radiography is used to detect features of a component or assembly that exhibit a difference in thickness or physical density as compared to surrounding material. Large differences are more easily detected than small ones. Specifically radiography can detect only those features that have an appreciable dimension parallel to the radiation beam. This means that the ability of the technique to detect planar discontinuities such as cracks depends on proper orientation of the test pieces during inspection. Thus cracks cannot be detected unless they are parallel to the radiation beam. Tight cracks in thick sections usually cannot be detected at all, even when properly orientated.

Delaminations in composites are nearly impossible to detect with radiography. Discontinuities such as voids can only be detected if they are of appreciable size in relation to specimen thickness and exhibit an absorption that differs by 2% or more from that of the surrounding material.

Subject contrast then, is the primary concern in the radiographic examination of composite materials and as stated this results from a change of density within the material.

Penetrant Enhanced X-radiography (PEXR)

In CFC composites both the fibre and the organic resin matrix materials have a high carbon content and therefore absorb X-rays similarly; also both differ only slightly in absorption properties from that of air. In order to provide a viable inspection technique to assess the extent of damage, subject contrast must be enhanced. This is achieved by the introduction of a contrast medium, usually referred to as a radio-opaque penetrant, and the method by which it is employed is termed penetrant-enhanced X-radiography (PEXR).

Alternative composite materials such as glass, kevlar, and boron fibre composites exhibit slightly different absorption characteristics from CFC, nevertheless all are greatly enhanced by the introduction of a radio-opaque penetrant into an area of damage.

The penetrant used must:

- (1) Be safe to use with normal precautions.
- (2) Not harm the material.

- (3) Have suitable radio-opacity.
- (4) Propagate to the full extent of damage.
- (5) Be removable.

Early successful work in the field of PEXR involved the use of tetrabromoethane (TBE) and diiodobutane (DIB). Both are extremely effective, particularly (TBE), but the special precautions demanded by the toxic nature of these compounds make them unsuitable for use other than in strictly controlled environments.

The most widely used penetrant, however, has been a super-saturated solution of the inorganic salt zinc iodide in iso-propyl alcohol. This is a non-toxic compound and although not providing quite the radiographic opacity of the two organics is, nevertheless, very effective. One problem though with the use of a salt such as zinc iodide for certain applications, such as in-service inspection, is that of subsequent removal. Organic solvents evaporate naturally, or with minimal heating, at an acceptable rate.

It was to investigate possible alternative and less toxic organic compounds and to evaluate their performance on a range of composite samples that a contract was placed with BAe Weybridge. Some of the results of this work and of a concurrent programme at RAE are given here.

It is naturally of prime concern that the penetrants used should in no way affect the matrix properties with a resultant loss in composite mechanical strength. Tests have been conducted by BAe and RAE and are continuing to investigate this. A double cantilever beam specimen produced by inserting a wedge at the mid-plane of a simple beam was used by BAe to examine the effects of organic penetrants on the resin matrix. A daily application of these penetrants over a 6-month period showed no increase in the length of edge cracks originally induced.

After a screening of possible penetrants on the grounds of safety and radiographic suitability a short list of 10 organic and 4 inorganic compounds was considered. These compounds are shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively and have been allotted a rating of relative radiographic opacity, compounds at the top of the list giving the highest contrast. In comparing the two tables zinc iodide, the only feasible inorganic penetrant, would be given a relative rating of 2 in Table 1.

**RELATIVE RADIOGRAPHIC OPACITY
OF ORGANIC PENETRANTS**

<u>Halogenated Hydrocarbon</u>	<u>RELATIVE RATING</u>
Di iodomethane	1
Di iodobutane	
Dibromomethane	2
Tetrachloroethylene	3
Tetrachloroethane	
Tetrachloromethane	4
Trichloroethylene	
Trichloroethane	5
Dichloromethane	
Trichlorotrifluoroethane	6

INORGANIC PENETRANTS

<u>Inorganic Compound</u>	<u>Opacity</u>
Zinc Iodide	High
Silver Nitrate	Medium
Lead Nitrate	Low
Barium Sulphate	Very low

(Zinc Iodide compares with dibromomethane)
(group 2)

TABLE 1 ORGANIC PENETRANTS

TABLE 2 INORGANIC PENETRANTS

The choice of penetrant for a particular application is most influenced by the degree of damage. For example, in a situation where ballistic impact has resulted in complete skin penetration, damage might be expected to be gross. In these circumstances high contrast group 1 and 2 compounds are absorbed in such quantity that any possibility of evaluating fine detail is lost. This type of damage assessment is better served by a low contrast penetrant from perhaps, group 5 or 6 when the quantity absorbed will offset the relative weaker enhancement. Conversely the BVID form of damage is likely to require a degree of enhancement obtainable only from group 1 or 2 compounds.

Figure 12 shows 2 examples of the resolution attainable using this technique. Translaminar cracking produced as a result of impact damage is readily seen extending from an area of delamination. To even approach this sensitivity would be extremely difficult using ultrasonic techniques.

Figure 12 PEXR of Impact Damage in CFC

In considering the possible application of these compounds for in-service use on CFC structures it should be noted that the lower four rated organic compounds from Table 1 are currently in use by the RAF for other purposes and would therefore be acceptable under normal handling procedures.

The full analysis capability of PEXR can only be fully realised if stereoscopy is employed. This technique requires that two separate radiographs are taken of a single object, one normal to the X-ray beam and the other at an angle to the beam appropriate to specimen thickness and source to film distance. The use of a 3-dimensional presentation via a stereo projector or a bench stereo viewer maximises the advantages of radiography and is the most sensitive NDE technique for composites. The angular separation can be obtained by either tilting the source or the specimen to match the subsequent eye viewing angle.

The volatility of some of the organic compounds is extremely important when stereo PEXR is employed. Any change in relative enhancement between the two film exposures virtually negates the technique.

Obviously PEXR has a very limited application for production inspection but its capability of providing a means of high resolution damage characterisation will continue to be exploited in the laboratory. The full implications of the regular use of PEXR for

in-service inspection of composite structures are currently being studied and will be referred to later.

Computer Aided Tomography (CAT)

A conventional radiograph is a two-dimensional presentation of a three-dimensional object, the density of the image at each point in the radiograph being governed by the total attenuation of that part of the X-ray beam. There is no information on the contribution that each element of the object makes to the total attenuation.

CAT on the other hand measures the intensity of X-ray transmission along many paths in a single plane. After this procedure has been repeated at many angles in the plane a computer is used to process the data and to calculate the attenuation contributed by each point in the plane. The result is displayed as a cross-sectional slice. In practice either a highly collimated beam is used with a single detector, or a fan beam is used with an array of detectors.

The nature of the manipulation system depends very much on the size of the component. For small components it is often convenient for the source and detector to remain fixed whilst the object is scanned and rotated. For large objects either the lateral scan or the rotation may be achieved by moving the source and detector. The wide use made of CAT as an invaluable diagnostic technique in the medical field has led to the development of equipment using low radiation doses giving moderate resolution but operating at high speed. For many industrial purposes higher energy and improved resolution are desirable, but medical units can be used on composite components of suitable geometry and have proved very valuable. Figure 3 was in fact obtained using an unmodified medical body scanner.

Thermography

Thermographic methods may be conveniently divided into two main types; passive - where there is an externally applied heating or cooling source and, active - where there are internally generated heating or cooling effects. In both cases the surface temperature distribution is monitored and examined for anomalies that indicate the presence of defects. The active method, however, has only really found application in the monitoring of fatigue tests where heat is generated by fretting effects at internal damage.

In the passive method, which has been much more widely employed, the surface of a component is subjected to a rapid temperature change and the subsequent heat flow monitored. A variety of heat sources have been investigated varying from simple hot-air guns to banks of flash tubes. The way in which the heat is dissipated depends on the thermal conductivity of the composite and on the nature and location of any defects. If there is a delamination in a laminate, for example, then less heat will be transmitted through the defective area resulting in a hot spot on the heated surface, and a cold spot on the back surface. It is possible to monitor either the front or the back surface (provided that this is accessible). By analogy

with ultrasonics terminology the former is often called a pulse-echo technique and the latter through-transmission.

It is usual for some kind of infra-red sensitive camera to be used and for the output to be stored on video tape. Not only does this permit subsequent viewing in real time, or at some other rate, but it also allows image processing techniques to be applied if necessary.

The performance of thermographic systems is, of course, strongly affected by the thermal conductivity of the particular composite. In CFC, for example, the conductivity in the plane of the laminate is about nine times that in the through-thickness direction. This transverse diffusion tends to obscure defects that are not close to the surface. However, as can be seen from Figure 8c the usual through-thickness distribution of impact damage is such that a damaged area that is large enough to be structurally significant will contain limited but measurable damage close to the surface. Thus thermography should be capable of detecting the presence of impact damage without having an ability to characterise it.

Pulsed video thermography has been developed and used successfully at the NDT centre at Harwell¹⁴ using a thermal TV camera and a range of thermal sources. This work has shown significant differences between the through-transmission and pulse-echo techniques used for double or single-sided examination respectively. The through-transmission technique can detect deeper defects than a pulse-echo approach. However, for defects near the surface the dimension and depth resolution obtainable with pulse-echo examination are superior. Using thermography on a variety of composite specimens this work has demonstrated an ability to detect impact damage in CFC material and delamination/disbonds in thin skinned CFRP and GRP honeycomb components.

Eddy Currents

Eddy currents, widely used as an inspection method for metallic materials, can be applied to composite materials containing conducting fibres but techniques differ to compensate for the comparatively very high resistivity. As an example CFC has approximately 100 times the resistivity of a typical stainless steel.

Eddy currents induced in a material by an adjacent current carrying coil, affect the impedance of the coil. Flaws within the material interrupt the eddy current field and change the coil impedance further. The response to a flaw is usually characterised in terms of amplitude and phase angle. The value of these will depend on probe parameters, material conductivity and thickness, and flaw dimensions. The spatial response of a probe, ie its sensitivity to a given size of flaw, is dependent on both the geometry of the coil and the driving frequency.

The frequencies used in eddy current inspection normally range from 200 Hz to 6 MHz or more. Selection of frequency is the normal compromise between penetration and resolution; high frequencies

result in higher resolution but a decreased depth of penetration. For CFC, however, the resistivity is very high so that penetration depth is not normally a problem even at quite high frequencies. For aerospace applications it has been found satisfactory to work at around 1 MHz.

In a conducting fibre composite eddy current techniques appear to be complementary to ultrasonics in that they are insensitive to delaminations and non-conducting inclusions but responsive to the broken fibres associated with impact damage, lightning strike, and similar structural component damage. As might be expected, eddy current response is extremely sensitive to fibre content. It is possible to measure a 20-30% variation in conductivity for a 3% variation in fibre content. Also since the penetration depth is usually quite large, a response is also obtained to quite small changes in thickness.

Acoustic Emission

In the acoustic emission technique a moderate, representative stress is applied to a component and sensitive transducers are used to monitor the occurrence of any failure events. Depending on the degree of sophistication of the instrumentation employed, information can be obtained on the nature, severity and location of the resultant stress waves (acoustic emissions); this information can often be used to reveal the presence of defects and sometimes to predict the stress at which failure will occur. The literature available on applications of AE to composites is now very extensive and cannot conveniently be summarised in this review, but it may be helpful to make some brief comments.

Even on quite simple specimens it is not easy to distinguish between the emissions from different types of failure event. Also composite materials introduce quite severe attenuation and dispersion of the stress waves and this usually means that quite a large number of transducers are required to monitor most practical structures adequately. The most successful applications have been when proof tests have been performed on a significant number of components allowing patterns of behaviour to be established. However, the stage at which emission restarts during a repeated loading (the Felicity effect) has also been shown to provide valuable information on individual components, including some quite complex fabrications.

Mechanical Impedance

There is currently available a range of inspection instruments, mainly designed for adhesive bond testing, that can be used with composite components and which operate on the principle of monitoring the response of a structure to some form of controlled mechanical excitation.

A typical application of this method involves the use of a transducer containing a pair of crystals rigidly joined one above the other.

The upper crystal is the exciter driven by a low frequency sinusoidal pulse. In free air both crystals vibrate in unison; there is no strain on the lower receiving coil and therefore no output. When the outer surface of the receiver is placed on a surface the crystal detects a restriction of movement. This produces a strain in the receiving crystal and a consequent output signal. The degree of restriction is governed by a combination of the local stiffness and the mass of material in the structure beneath the transducer. This degree of stiffness is normally displayed either as amplitude of received signal or the difference in phase angle between the transmitted and received signals.

To inspect a component using this technique, it is necessary to first calibrate on a known "good" area of structure and then an area of known disbond. The optimum frequency of excitation to produce maximum response is then established. Typically this will lie between 1 and 10 kHz.

This method is most sensitive to defects between a thin top layer and a stiff substructure and the sensitivity drops rapidly with defect depth. It is particularly suited to the detection of disbonds in thin-skinned honeycomb structures. Recent work¹⁵ has shown that on CFC-skinned honeycomb panels a 10 mm defect could reliably be found under a 0.5 mm thick skin but not under a 1 mm thick skin. Of interest also was the observation that detection of a constant size defect beneath a constant skin thickness was greatly affected by varying the depth of the honeycomb. Up to an optimum thickness, an increase produced increasing sensitivity.

An alternative mechanical impedance technique measures the force induced in a structure due to a low frequency controlled impulse loading. The resultant pulse shape or its Fourier transform can then be displayed. These will be dependent on local stiffness and can provide information over a range of frequencies unlike the fixed frequency approach described above.

Inspection of Adhesive Bonded Joints

Adhesive bonding of one composite component to another is, of course, an integral part of many structural fabrications and there is an increasing trend to use adhesive bonding to join composite and metallic components. In the past the integrity of these bonds has largely been assured by rigorous process control and inspection has been confined to detection of areas of disbond. This can usually readily be achieved by ultrasonic techniques similar to those used to find delaminations, or by the use of one of the wide range of commercial bond testers which respond to in various ways to the mechanical impedance of the component.

Measurement of the cohesive strength within the adhesive layer, or of the adhesive strength of the bond between adhesive and adherend, is however a much more difficult task. This has been discussed at some length in a recent report¹⁶ which concluded that it was the

adhesive strength that was of primary concern and pointed out that the problems of metallic and composite adherends are very different.

In broad terms the joint between a composite adherend and an adhesive layer is a simple joint between two essentially similar materials. Furthermore, if such a joint is satisfactory immediately after fabrication then environmental degradation is not a major problem. The main problem would appear to be contamination of the surface prior to bonding and this may be resolvable with high resolution ultrasonics. With metallic adherends the situation is much more complex. In order to obtain a satisfactory bond it is necessary to prepare the surface by etching and/or anodising to produce a controlled oxide layer. Characterisation of the morphology of the oxide layer may well permit as-manufactured adhesive strength to be measured, but it is the prediction of the degree of susceptibility to environmental degradation that is of prime concern. At present it appears that some sophisticated form of ultrasonic interrogation may be capable of monitoring the extent to which degradation has taken place but the required prediction capability cannot yet be met.

PRODUCTION INSPECTION

The production inspection of CFC components requires a different approach from that applied to laboratory specimens or to the in-service inspection of composite structures. The techniques employed must not only be cost effective and capable of matching production rates, but also and most importantly, be capable of reliably detecting defects to a required standard.

For a number of components quite simple techniques are adequate. It is, for example, possible to get useful information about the quality of quite thick GRP components by examining them visually against a brightly lit background. Similarly, large disbonds can often be found by a simple coin tap test and an experienced operator can extract a good deal of information using a commercial bond tester. Beyond this, however heavy emphasis is placed on ultrasonics and radiography.

The principal inspection method for the majority of aerospace components is through-transmission ultrasonics. Immersion tanks for the most part being impractical, components are normally suspended vertically in a frame and the probes aligned horizontally. Water jet (squitter) probes supply a collimated laminar flow couplant path for the ultrasonic beam, and C-scan recordings are made in a variety of ways from straight mechanical linkages to remote computer storage.

It should be appreciated that through-transmission inspection is only capable of presenting defect size and position and that no further information related to depth is possible. For example, to determine if the detected defect in a typical skin/honeycomb component is a skin delamination, a skin-adhesive disbond, an adhesive-core disbond or crushed honeycomb, requires alternative methods. If it is necessary to characterise the defect then other NDT methods must be used such as pulse-echo ultrasonics, radiography, mechanical impedance, and bond testing techniques.

Where, because of the particular component application, water coupled ultrasonic techniques are precluded then dry coupled roller probes may be used on solid components and non-couplant mechanical impedance methods on composite-skinned honeycomb components. If it is necessary to avoid any possibility of contamination then air-coupled ultrasonics is feasible but this requires much higher energies and lower frequencies.

Conventional X-radiography, as previously discussed, is of little practical use in the detection of planar defects but can be particularly useful in the detection of porosity and cracking at radii; here orientation of the X-ray beam at a tangent offers a possible solution to a difficult inspection problem.

Currently in the UK aerospace industry the standard for fixed wing military composite components specifies an ability to detect interlaminar defects of 36 mm^2 in all production items. In order to maintain defect detectability in cases of tapered or slightly curved structure the principle of using external lead tabs has been employed. These strips of lead foil are bonded to the surface of the component in the critical areas and act as defects of control size by appearing on the C-scans providing a calibration check. They also serve as convenient positional markers when radiography is used as a complementary technique.

As noted earlier, when considering the requirements for inspection, radiography is widely used for inspecting composite rotor components for aircraft. Interpretation is, however, a skilled procedure requiring background experience on these particular types of component.

IN-SERVICE INSPECTION

When considering the needs of in-service inspection it is obviously necessary first to determine the critical defect size and then to decide on a technique that is capable of meeting the requirements reliably and economically. There should be, for instance, no requirement to inspect to a level of sensitivity greater than that employed during production and for the majority of applications the practical difficulties of on-site inspection dictate a greatly reduced defect detectability.

It is likely therefore that, for most composite applications and certainly for aerospace structures, the first inspection method will be visual. Examination of surfaces for indications of impact damage will be the most used method and in fact, in the case of one first generation composite military aerospace structure, no visible indication of damage is regarded by the manufacturer as being satisfactory clearance¹⁷. Although in this particular case there is evidence from structural testing and operating experience to suggest that this advice is not too optimistic, there are nevertheless good reasons for adopting a more cautious approach. For example, experience with such structures is somewhat limited and it is not possible to perform structural tests to cover all eventualities. It is also felt that experience gained on this particular structure, which is rather conservatively designed,

will provide the basis for inspection techniques for next generation structures in which the significant defects may well be smaller and sub-surface.

Now some of the inspection techniques already reviewed in this paper may be ideally suited to support laboratory studies of material properties or the requirements of production inspection but may be totally impractical for in-service needs. For example an inspector may be faced with a requirement to check the 8 m height of an A310 Airbus fin, the 22 m² area of a Harrier GR5 wing, or a 30 m long GRP minehunter hull. These three applications have very different constructions and therefore the requirements for in-service inspection are unlikely to be the same; furthermore, none of the structures is particularly suited to immersion ultrasonics which is probably the preferred laboratory technique. The basic inspection methods, however, will be the same as those previously discussed, with the addition of impact sensitive coatings and fibre optics which are specific to in-service investigations and will be discussed later.

It is the intention then in this section to re-examine these methods and assess their suitability to meet practical inspection problems. This will primarily be done by reference to aerospace structures but the conclusions are likely to be applicable to the whole range of composite structures.

For most in-service inspections there are two basic requirements;

- a. defect detection
- b. defect characterisation (type, size and position).

Where there is no surface visible damage the first of these two is probably the most difficult since there is a need to reliably find a specified size of defect over a large area relatively quickly. It is likely that surfaces may not be optimum, thicknesses may vary, and in most cases there will be supporting sub-structure. Consideration of these factors will influence the choice of inspection method and, as a consequence, dictate the level of sensitivity.

In-service Inspection Techniques

The most common method and the logical first approach is that of some form of visual inspection. A possible technique particularly suited to specific critical areas of the structure is to use a "witness coating".

Impact Sensitive Coatings

An apparently simple way of revealing that an impact has taken place is to paint the accessible surface with an impact-sensitive coating. This is usually in the form of a micro-encapsulated dye which is released when crushed. This approach is very attractive because it provides a simple visual indication of areas requiring further inspection. It may, however, be difficult to ensure that the response is unambiguous. The coating must of course be able to with-

stand minor day-to-day damage, including abrasion, without giving an indication. Rather more important than this, however, is the fact that the damage induced by a specific impactor is strongly influenced by the geometry of the structure and in particular by the nature of the supporting sub-structure. There is as yet little evidence on the relationship between the normal bearing stresses and the resultant sub-surface damage even on quite simple components.

It is of course possible to examine a normal painted surface for signs of foreign body impact but in the case of a current military aircraft the painted surface is usually given a life of from 5 to 6 years. It might be expected over this period that a considerable amount of surface abrasion would occur raising a problem of incident dating and of logging the subsequent inspection to avoid duplication.

Ultrasonic Methods

The choice of ultrasonic technique and consequent sensitivity will be governed by composite type, quality and thickness. GRP for example is considerably more attenuative than CFC and a porous, thick GRP component will therefore dictate a quite different inspection approach from that required for thin, high quality CFC material. The inspection requirements must obviously reflect this. Furthermore it should be noted when using ultrasonic techniques that defects located beneath other defects will not normally be quantifiable or even detectable.

Possibly the simplest ultrasonic approach, and also one of the cheapest in terms of equipment cost, is to use a digital thickness gauge. This small hand-held device when correctly calibrated with appropriate sound velocity should give a read-out of thickness matching the component design. An interlaminar defect will be indicated at its through-thickness position and there should be no question of an inability to identify impact damage using this device. However, the need of a couplant, the small probe diameter and the fact that there is no means of data storage indicate a use more suited to defect characterization than detection. Also in a component such as an aircraft wing-skin, where thickness varies in a complex form from tip to root over a sub-structure of spars, any attempt to scan an area might prove difficult to interpret. A possible solution which would enable such a unit to be used for defect detection might be to incorporate a gate. As noted when discussing thermography, structurally significant impact damage will have elements that lie close to the surface. The gate could be set to interrogate only down to a depth slightly less than the minimum thickness of the skin. Variations in thickness, or the presence of sub-structure would then not be a problem, no change from the set datum would indicate a composite very probably free from impact damage.

An alternative ultrasonic technique more suited to detection over a large area would be to make use of roller probes. These do have the attraction of not requiring a couplant and by using a number in unison should be capable of scanning at reasonable speed. Sensitivity is not high but typically a 20 mm diameter defect should not be missed in good quality CFC of 15 mm thickness.

The use of a multi-element ultrasonic transducer, although requiring a couplant, would provide an ability both to detect defects and to provide a degree of characterization not possible with either of the preceding techniques.

There is an increasing number of commercial ultrasonic systems which provide an in-situ scanning facility, are able to inspect aerofoil curvatures, and to output information to some form of data storage unit. Information obtained is normally in a C-scan format with probe position and signal amplitude displayed on a TV monitor. Scanning frames are sometimes used but because of their rigidity hand scanning is preferred, probe position being monitored by a variety of means. Some systems can also provide a display in which signal amplitude is related to depth in order to provide information on through-thickness position of the defect. Robotic systems which are currently in use for production inspection of certain composite aerospace components might also be adapted for in-service needs.

A variety of ultrasonic techniques are therefore available for both the detection and characterisation of in-service defects and where there is no surface damage these provide the most accurate inspection method. Where there is surface damage, penetrant enhanced X-radiography is capable of providing greater sensitivity in less time than with ultrasonics but it must of course be possible to locate the film in a suitable position behind the back surface.

Radiography

PEXR has the ability to image impact damage in composites that will not only provide the delamination detail available using high frequency ultrasonics but also display associated translaminal cracking that ultrasonics is likely to miss. Such information is extremely useful, for instance, when a decision has to be made on the area to be repaired. Of course there will be areas of a structure where the use of PEXR will not be possible. For example, there must obviously be surface access for the penetrant to be introduced, and the low energy level X-rays will be completely absorbed by any metallic components such as the erosion protection strip on a wing leading edge. However, when the technique can be used it is an attractive method to determine the extent of surface visible damage.

Thermography

It seems likely that increasing use will be made of the ability to visualise heat dissipation in composite structures. The attraction of a non-contact, rapid area assessment to detect defects is considerable. In the authors' opinion this is the true strength of this inspection method and although detectability at depth may be a problem, there will be enough near-surface damage from impact loads to make this method potentially the most attractive for damage detection. Although there are some sophisticated data processing techniques that can provide a certain degree of defect characterization using thermography, at present ultrasonics and PEXR are more suited to this task.

Eddy Currents

The possible use of eddy-currents to detect damage in CFC also has the attraction of not requiring a couplant and could be reasonably rapid. However, as previously mentioned, the problems of sensitivity to fibre content and thickness variations, plus that of spurious readings caused by metallic fasteners limit their use to simple components.

Fibre Optics

Simple optical fibres bonded to the surface of metallic structures have recently shown some promise as a cheap and simple method of monitoring the initiation of cracks in specific areas which are inaccessible, yet known to be vulnerable. When a crack occurs in the metal the optical fibre breaks and light transmission is sharply decreased. It has been proposed that similar fibres could be laid up as an integral part of a composite structure and monitored to detect say, damage or overload. The first point to note is that most optical fibres have a diameter of about 100 micrometres, which is much larger than structural glass or carbon fibres, and it must be verified that they do not have a detrimental affect on the structural performance. It also seems likely that in the case of impact damage the discontinuity provided by an optical fibre might encourage delamination along its plane; if so the optical fibre would not break. If, alternatively, the optical fibres are required to break when overstressed then it will be necessary to give them a carefully controlled surface treatment in order to reduce the strength in an predictable and repeatable manner.

CONCLUSIONS

It is possible to inspect composite materials in many ways and to impose widely varying acceptance standards. Ideally the requirements for inspection should be derived from a knowledge of the failure processes likely to occur in a particular component, and of the role that specific defects play in these failure processes. In practice, however, acceptance standards are frequently established on the basis of past experience.

Although a number of features could potentially be regarded as defects, with the current generation of materials the types of defect sought in practice are very limited. Provided that there is the correct quantity of fibres aligned in the required directions then what are primarily sought are delaminations and gross porosity.

The most universally employed NDE method is some form of ultrasonic interrogation and the available techniques vary widely in complexity and capability. Radiography is also extensively used and its usefulness is much increased by the addition, where possible of radio-opaque penetrants. Of the many other methods that can be employed perhaps thermography and mechanical impedance techniques show the most promise.

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